

Developing Policy Instruments to Reduce Inequality of Land Ownership

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ABSTRACT: This research is motivated by the inequality of land ownership and policies regarding restrictions on land ownership. However, existing policies have not been able to resolve the problem of inequality in land ownership. The study was conducted using a qualitative approach with a perspective theoretical instrument policy. Primary data was obtained from observation during three months of study fields and interviews with a profound amount of key informants, the head of Government, the village chief, local peasants/local people, and communities. Research results show that the instrument policy of land that is used is not using a practical instrument such as land value reference, added value capturing, and land taxation. Land value reference, added value capturing, and land taxation can be used to reduce land inequality in Bandung Regency. Land value reference will create land market transparency, added value capturing will reduce the appearance of land speculators, and land taxation will effectively deter the person ruling the land. Instruments policy of land practically contributes to reducing idle lands, increasing the growth of the economy, creating field jobs, adding state income, reducing inequality in the economy, and improving the well-being of people.

KEYWORDS: Instrument policies, Instruments policy of land, Inequality of land ownership.

INTRODUCTION

According to Howlett and Ramesh (1995), instruments policy is conceptualized as a device policy used by the Government in using applicable policy. This method is used in implementation policy and election target policy. There are three instrument policies, such as Voluntary Instrument, that place the Government in a non-decision position because of the perspective government that the best policy is conducted directly by target policy. A binding instrument is an instrument that could direct an individual with a base policy. Then, a hybrid instrument is an instrument that combines the instrument mandatory and instrument volunteer. Gerber et al. (2018) policy land is used to solve the problem of the regular public related to the use of land that is inadequate or causes distraction. Through different instrument policies, public policies aim to change the behavior of a group or can be classified as a society or people that can be the roots or source of the problem that we solve delve to avoid a negative outcome or consequences from the problem that is at hand for the group best of interest. Policy instruments of land use by using public policies without affecting property rights consist of 3 instruments: land value reference, added value capturing, and land taxation. Land value reference is an instrument that requires information on the development of land prices in the market and the land policy. Added value capturing is the change in land prices caused by changes in the function of the land area. Land taxation is a tax levied on the ownership and use of land. (Gerber, Hengstermann, and Hartmann, 2018)

Inequality of land ownership has been a problem faced by Indonesia since ancient times. A solution is needed to increase land ownership distribution in Indonesia so that people can live prosperously, as aspired to in the 1945 Constitution. With a firm policy regarding land tenure restrictions, it can be an opportunity for people to live prosperously in the future. Inequality in the agrarian sector is divided into two categories (Shohibuddin, 2019): inequality of distribution and inequality of allocation. Inequality of distribution is explained as the gap in the ownership of the land between classes by sector of agriculture people. At the same time, inequality of allocation is explained as the gap in agrarian sources between sectors. Inequality of distribution and inequality of allocation is what Indonesia is facing since then until now. Inequality of distribution can be seen by what is happening now, for example, the massive layoffs that are been done by peasants from the agricultural sector, not because of finding better job opportunities in sectors other than agriculture, but because they are no longer accommodated in the agricultural sector. Because of no longer being accommodated in the sector of agriculture. As quoted by (Pujriyani et al., 2016), there is a tendency for young people to leave the agricultural sector. One of the influencing factors is land ownership. Inequality of allocation occurs because no one could mandate the UUPA to operate in favor of allocation to interest people, and inequality increased sharply during reform. Two types of inequality

in the agrarian sector disclose the situation in Indonesia: land as a basic material for production and the well-being of people only accumulated in those with capital. In the end, inequality on this basic material causes a gap in the economy of others.

According to data from the Ministry of Agrarian Affairs and Spatial Planning/ National Land Agency (2017), there are 3.58 million hectares of land that are abandoned and not being well maintained let alone being built of something that still has a Government permit. This area alone is compared to the total of land in the agriculture sector which only owns an area of 13.7 million and with that amount of land it could be used to accommodate more than 26 million local farmers' households (*Rumah Tangga Petani*) (Shohibuddin, 2019) Based on the data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), land ownership inequality in 2013 reached 0.68 up to 1 percent of Indonesian who controlled 68% of the land resources. This causes Indonesia to face a problem which is the emergency of land ownership inequality. This problem will become a very complex and chronic problem if it is not resolved.

Some regulations about rule restrictions on ownership of land in Indonesia, such as Law No. 5 of 1960 or more often called Act tree agrarian. In chapter 7, it is stated that this explains the *Groot grondbezitter*, namely prohibiting land ownership beyond the limit or latifundium. Efforts made by the government to reduce inequality in land ownership are carried out with agrarian reform programs. However, this program has not been running well and still raises a high level of inequality in land ownership. The government is trying to issue policies for the success of agrarian reform, but these policies do not contain practical instruments to increase equity in land ownership.

Inequality ownership was discussed about land in the study that occurred in Bandung Regency, especially in Margamulya Village, Pangalengan District. Bandung Regency has a mountainous topography with massive potential for agricultural land, especially in Margamulya Village. With the vast potential of agricultural land, there is a problem of inequality in land ownership in Bandung Regency. Land ownership in Bandung Regency is still dominantly owned by capital owners, causing local peasants not to be able to own land, as what happened in Margamulya Village, Bandung Regency.

Inequality of land ownership is a serious problem, and it is essential to be resolved immediately. Massive land tenure by capital owners is assumed to create economic growth. However, in reality, what happened was the economic inequality of the population was getting sharper. In addition, the impact is the exploitation of peasants. The perspective of land investment as a very profitable investment must be changed. Investment in land does not increase economic growth but hampers the growth of the economy. It's because there will be a lot of land still not productive (idle), which can be used to encourage economic growth. This investment will also lead to the emergence of land speculators.

The prohibition on land ownership by latifundium was established to end the inequality of land ownership and reduce the accumulation of land in the hands of certain people or groups. Land ownership that exceeds the limit will harm the public interest, create landlords, and have other adverse impacts, such as not increasing production; locals have to pay rent for land, and rent will keep on increasing with that being said the locals won't be able to have increased incomes.

On the other hand, some studies about the inequality of land had been done both inside and outside of the country many times. Meanwhile, the study abroad, Wegerif and Guarena (2020) carried out a study that aims to determine the driving factors for land tenure trends. The results showed the increasing land ownership inequality which causes most locals to own very little amount of land. The elite and big corporations control most agricultural sectors, so locals and workers have little income. Another study shows how the relationship between land inequality and riots in rural areas shows that the relationship between land inequality and the riots that occur is conditional; there is a relationship between land invasion and the elite land rulers (Albertus et al., 2018). Furthermore, the impact of land inequality on conflict intensity is the most severe conflict that can occur at the medium level of land inequality.

The research conducted in Indonesia shows that, in essence, agrarian reform is an asset reform (asset management) and access reform (access arrangement) that goes hand in hand to manage unequal land tenure to realize agrarian justice (agrarian justice). (Ramdani, 2020)

According to Winoto (2007) many as 37.17 million people in Indonesia still live below the poverty line, 66 percent of them are in rural areas, and 56 percent live depending on the agricultural sector. According to estimates (Suhendar, 1995), about 60% of the total locals are locals who do not own land. Some are agricultural laborers, and others work on other people's land as tenants or cultivators with profit-sharing provisions. Dealing with the problems of inequality and poverty, it is urgent to accelerate policies that can reorganize land ownership and resource control so that justice is realized in the control and use of resources.

Therefore, this study considers it essential to see and explore why policy instruments have not been optimal in reducing land inequality. Based on the description above, this study aims to provide recommendations for appropriate policy instruments to reduce inequality in land ownership in Bandung Regency.

METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach. Creswell (2013) suggested that qualitative research is carried out to understand as deeply as possible so that the structure of knowledge that comes from the researchers can be delivered to the participants, spending much time on research and digging up information to get detailed information. To explore new information and understand the complexity of the meaning of social interaction of Margamulya Village communities in managing the village's natural resources, this study used in-depth interviews conducted in an open and semi-structured manner. Data gathering is also done through observation and document study. The field research was carried out in five visits from April to July 2022.

Interviews were conducted with several key informants consisting of village leaders such as the head of the village administration section and the head of Government, elements of the village community, and locals. Through observation, researchers can cross-check or add data and information obtained from the in-depth interviews that have been done or search documents or archives to obtain more detailed information and descriptions of the conditions in the field. Document studies are carried out by searching, collecting, mapping, processing, and analyzing secondary data, including 1) village data, 2) legal documents, and 3) other relevant documents, such as articles/manuscript reports related to the research.

The data that has been collected is then analyzed. The analysis results provide a basis for researchers to interpret the data to understand deeply the implied meanings of various interactions and social processes that reflect reality in the field. Furthermore, the processing and analysis of field data are carried out by organizing and sorting the data out. The qualitative data analysis technique in this study adopted the analysis stage model suggested by Yin (2015), such as data compilation, data sorting and classification, data rearrangement, data interpretation, and conclusion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bandung Regency is an area with high natural resource potential because it's located in the mountains with a natural hilly area with an expanse of plantation tea. The most excellent potential is the results of the nature objects traveling. Object tours are dominated by ecotourism, combining tour nature and commodity agriculture production. Most of the people of Bandung Regency are agriculturists; a thing that causes a high number of inequalities in Bandung Regency.

Margamulya Village is a village with the majority of residents being an agriculturist. Village clans have about 1,294.14 hectares (Village Monograph, 2022). With pattern ownership land in the village clan, 90% of the land is owned by the corporation. The remaining 10% of land ownership is controlled by people with money that is also used for rent for the public. The chart of land ownership in Margamulya Village below shows ownership of land lame in the village clan.

Figure 1. Land Ownership in the Margamulya Village

Source: Survey Results, 2022

Based on the results of Interviews with the Head of Margamulya Village Government Office, the Head of Hamlet 3 in Margamulya Village, and one local in the village clan, they say that land ownership in the village can be counted with fingers. They also explained that the ownership of a big land is owned by the village government, a corporation like Public Forestry Company (Perhutani), and Archipelago Plantation Public Company (PTPN), and last, only some of the local villagers have their land. In the village community, most of the local people or agriculturists work on the land belonging to someone else.

From the data obtained by interviewing 48 local villagers, The merged Margamulya Village in a cooperative effort of locals and agriculturists, the majority of the working land owned by corporation. System rent per 1 spear land is 5 thousand rupiahs per year (Survey Finding, 2022). Whereas if peasants rent land owned by someone else, the rent price can reach 15 thousand per spear. The rent still belonged to cheap and affordable peasants. However, if peasants work large enough land, they rent this enough burden. The price is rent land corporation; however, if rent land is owned by personnel, then the rent will be different and more expensive.

Figure 1. Chart Of Land Tenure By 3 Peasant Groups In Margamulya Village

Source: Survey Results, 2022

The data above showed that of the 48 peasants included in the three-group peasants, 85 percent of them rent land not enough of 2 hectares. This shows that high inequality causes peasants unable to own 0.5 hectares of land to farm.

Government village clan trouble is for raise price rent land is hard, because remembers the results peasants who do not determine will become troublesome public in pay rent land more. Farming also requires other costs such as medicine, fertilizer, and other things. Laborer peasants in Margamulya Village paid 40 thousand rupiahs per day for men and 35 thousand rupiahs per day for females. (Survey Finding, 2022)

This Thing shows the reason for the persistent poverty increase. Poverty is one of the causes is structure mastery lame ground which results in the domination of one group on the group and makes the group lower peasants not have a strong base on that island. (Luthfi, 2011)

Bearing in mind this, the peasants' erratic income alone is already a burden, plus they have to pay annual rent. Therefore it is very urgent to solve the land problem as soon as possible for the welfare of the Indonesian people.

A. Land Policy Mapping

Figure 2. Land Ownership Policies in Indonesia

Source: Researcher, 2022.

Table 1. The Law Regarding Restriction On Land Ownership

No	Regulation	Rule Name	Instrument
1.	Law No. 20 of 1961	Revocation Act Rights to Land and the Objects On It	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For the interest general so revocation of the right on soil could be done for the sake of people.
2.	Law No.26 of 2007	Spatial Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The implementation of spatial planning aims to create a safe, comfortable, productive, and sustainable national territorial space.
3.	Law No. 23 of 1997	Management Act Environment Life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> source power naturally controlled by the government and used for the prosperity of the people, the arrangement set government Government arranges about supply, designation, use, and utilization of source power nature.
4.	Law No. 17 of 2017	Law on National Long-Term Development Plan 2005 – 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Management of land will be conducted efficiently and effectively with the applied principle of justice. Conducted improvement ownership of land through many rule implementations so that the community with the economy down gets land.

Source: Researcher 2022.

Table 2. Government Regulations Regarding Restrictions On Land Ownership

No	Regulation	Rule Name	Instrument
1.	Government Regulation No. 56 of 1960	Implementation of Land Distribution and Giving Change Loss	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> person or the head with land exceeding the limit large maximum Required report self to head agrarian in the area.
2.	Government Regulation No. 19 of 2021	Maintenance Land Procurement for Development Interest General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> land taken by the state will be given appropriate and fair compensation.

Source: Researcher 2022.

Table 3. President Regulations Regarding Restrictions On Land Ownership

No	Regulation	Rule Name	Instrument
1.	President Regulation No. 56 of 2006,	Maintenance Land Procurement for Development Interest General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> land taken by the state will be given appropriate and fair compensation.
2.	President Regulation No. 10 of 2006	National Land Agency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the National Land Agency must supervise and control mastery of land ownership.
3.	President Regulation No. 86 of 2018	Reform agrarian	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reform agrarian conducted to reduce inequality mastery and ownership of soil for creating justice. That reform agrarian conducted with method redistribution of land and legalization assets.

Source: Researcher 2022.

Table 4. Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Regarding Restrictions on Land Ownership

No	Regulation	Rule Name	Instrument
1.	Minister of Home Affairs Regulation No. 15 the Year 1974	Guidelines Follow Carry on Implementation of Land Reform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land that exceeds the limit the solution held following provision applicable and mandatory regulations reported to the government.

Source: Researcher 2022.

Table 5. Head of the Land Agency Regulation Regarding Restrictions on Land Ownership

No	Regulation	Rule Name	Instrument
1.	Head of the National Land Agency Regulation No. 3 of 1991	Regulation Object Mastery Land reform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Landreform conducted to increase land distribution to peasant cultivators to increase their welfare.

Source: Researcher, 2022.

Policies about ownership of land have many implemented in Indonesia. Policies adhering to instrument policy, according to Howlet and Ramesh (1995:91) is a voluntary instruments, mandatory instruments and hybrid instruments (mixed instruments). However, the instruments used do not have practical instruments, so these policies have not solved the inequality in land ownership.

The voluntary Instruments instrument is an instrument that puts the Government in a non-decision position with the hope that the policy will run well if the community and other parties carry it out. Furthermore, the mandatory instrument is an instrument that

places the Government as a party that forces or directs individuals with policies. Lastly, hybrid instruments (mixed instruments) is an instrument that put the Government in the party that makes decisions and punishments for things that are not desirable.

An instrument is required in Act 5 of 1960 concerning Basic Basic Rules Fundamentals agrarian. Article 7 states that ownership or mastery of land that exceeds the limit is not allowed because it will be harmful general interest. Besides that, Article 9 contains instrument mixture as stated in Article 9 paragraph 2, which states that whole citizens have the same opportunity to get right on the land. Instrument mix is also confirmed in Article 17, paragraph 3, which is explained with the decision government take excess land from the limit maximum for shared, as instead of giving change, make a loss for owner land.

Another regulation governing the revocation of suitable land and its replacement is Law No. 20 of 1961 concerning Revocation Rights to Land and the Objects On It. In this Law, an instrument Required as described in Article 1 is for the general interest, so revocation of right on the land could be done for the sake of the people.

The regulations governing ownership of land that is the policy about setting space. The regulation about setting rooms in Act Number 24 of 1992 concerns Spatial Planning. Chapter 2 explained that setting room conducted to use the room could Empower beneficial, harmonious, and balanced. In points policy, this use instrument volunteer or Government expect that policy walk well if done by the community.

The regulation about ownership there is also land in Act Number 23 of 1997 concerning the Management Environment live as explained in Article 8, which reads that source power is naturally controlled by the Government and used for the prosperity of the people, the arrangement set government. Government arranges about supply, designation, use, and utilization of source power nature.

Next, land ownership is also mentioned in Act Number 17 of 2007 concerning the National Long-Term Development Plan 2005 – 2025. Rule the mentioned that Management land will be conducted efficiently and effectively with application principle justice. Conducted improvement ownership land through many rule implementations so that the community with the economy down gets land.

Then rule ownership of land is also set in Regulation Government, like Regulation Government Number 56 of 1960, concerning Implementation of Land Distribution and Giving Change Losses. Chapter 3 explained that a person or the head with land exceeding the large limit maximum is required to report self to the head agrarian in the area. Powered by Regulation Government No. 19 of 2021 and Regulations President Number 56 Years 2006 about Maintenance Land Procurement for Development Interest General explained that land taken by the state would be given appropriate and fair compensation.

This rule supervised implementation by the National Land Agency following Regulation President Number 10 of 2006 concerning the National Land Agency, which is explained in Article 3 as the Duty of the National Land Agency is for To do supervision and control mastery of ownership of land. However, this has not been optimally proven with still height inequality in own land in Indonesia.

In resolving inequality government carried out the affirmed land reform program in Regulation Head of the Land Agency, Number 3 of 1991 concerning Regulation Object Land Mastery Landreform by Self-subsistent explained that land reform was conducted to increase land distribution to peasant cultivators to increase his welfare.

Then supported by the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation number 15 of 1974 concerning Guidelines Follow Carry on Implementation of Land Reform. Chapter II explained particularly about solution land above advantages maximum. Land that exceeds the limit the solution held following provision applicable and mandatory regulations reported to the Government.

Not stop until Land Reform, the Government is also doing agrarian reform for the whole problem of inequality in land in Indonesia. Reform agrarian the set in stipulation Assembly Indonesian People's Consultation (TAP MPR) No. IX/MPR/2001 concerning Update Agrarian and Management Source power nature. Reform agrarian conducted to arrange repeat ownership of land in Indonesia for certainty and protection law as well as the well-being of people.

Confirmed again in Regulation President Number 86 of 2018 About Reform agrarian. The destination did reform the agrarian listed in Article 2 to reduce inequality possession and possession of land for creating justice. Then explained that agrarian reform was carried out with the redistribution of land and legalization assets (Article 6).

With the amount very policy many about rule restrictions on ownership of land and government programs in reducing inequality in the land, policies are the only use instrument following the theory Howlet and Ramesh (1995:91) are mandatory, voluntary, and

mixed. These policies do not yet have practical instruments that directly provide a deterrent effect on unscrupulous individuals who think about excess land.

B. Land Policy Instruments

I. Land Value Reference

Land value reference is an essential dimension of the land. The actual value of land prices and general knowledge of market developments are essential for a healthy land market. Some countries decide to collect and publish information on the land market and actual transactions.

Instrument Land value reference no there is in policy land in Indonesia. Land prices are not published and informed to the public by area or are not listed in the policy. Not even in Indonesia is there a board of judge's land, so that cause no there is a specific price in the land market. This is also what often causes the appearance of speculators' land and improves inequality in own land in Indonesia.

Instrument Land value reference no exists in Indonesia; however, there is Sales Value of Taxable Object (NJOP) in the imposition of Land and Building Tax (PBB). However, these are two clear things clear different. Sales Value of Taxable Object (NJOP) is the average price of transaction sold to buy land reasonably. If there is no transaction, Sales Value of Taxable Object (NJOP) is determined by comparing price with a similar object, value acquisition new or score sell object tax substitute. This is why Indonesia does not have standard-price land that can be used as a reference.

As happened in the Margamulya Village, no reference base land price caused the Public to conclude alone price land from the ground zone. Based on the results Interview with the Head of Government Margamulya Village, there is no reference base price land in Margamulya Village. Village community concludes alone price land according to the zone. Price land located on the edge Street big will be more expensive than price land used as complex housing. Suppose the price of land in edge Street province is around 10-15 million rupiah per meter, while in the village, it can be around 2 million rupiahs per meter. Besides that example, another is when the public wants to buy land on edge Street. However, for sale, more height is fixed will be bought by the community; for example, the new one occurs in the area Mighty Hero of the land with an area of 100 spears for sale with the price of 1.5 billion.

The condition in the Margamulya Village is that individual landowners assess the price of land by looking at the condition of the land. There is no reference for land prices, and only Sales Value of Taxable Object (NJOP) can be used. The assessment using this Sales Value of Taxable Object (NJOP) is only to see whether the area has a high or low Sales Value of Taxable Object (NJOP). So the sale is only based on the people's desire to sell the land at their respective prices; the principle used is that when selling expensive land, no one will want to buy it, but when selling too cheap, it has no profit. In addition, land prices are also determined by land conditions, such as land on flat or steep fields.

An official land price reference is needed from the government to be used as an essential reference in selling and buying land so that there is no confusion among the public. The price of land will also follow the standards used so that no more land is too expensive or too cheap.

Policy land in Indonesia does not yet have an instrument Land value reference; land price is not yet published by transparent and official by the Government. Instrument Reference Land Value can use Government to create land market transparency, prevent speculators' land and reduce land ownership inequality, especially in Bandung Regency.

Instrument Land value reference is already used in several countries, such as Germany, Sweden, and Taiwan. Germany uses Land value reference as one instrument in policy land through an online platform BORIS. Land value reference showed based on results of the assessment of the board of judges carried out at least two years once. Land value reference showed with score specifically (euro per square meter). Instrument this proven create impact positive creates transparency in the land market in Germany and does not negatively impact society. (Voß & Bannert, 2018)

Different from Germany, Land value reference in Sweden no affect the land market but is used for giving information to actors in the land market for analysis more carry on in various things. Evaluation of land is conducted routinely with a period of different times; houses and condos are rated every three years once, while industry, agriculture, and forestry are rated every six years once. Evaluation this conducted shared Becomes number of areas with reference price Different lands are appraised from type property, area, water, waste status, year construction, standard buildings, and so on. (Kalbro & Norell, 2018)

One of the countries in Asia that uses Land value reference as one instrument in policy the land is Taiwanese. In Taiwan, the land must rate, and the price of land is announced to the public. Evaluation conducted repeat every three years once. Department administration land in every city is responsible for evaluating land by gathering the average price transaction of use land and value income land in 12 months last. Nevertheless, what happened in Taiwan was Land value reference that was not ignored by the community, so that caused an impact like the people who control many lands but pay tax few and speculators' land that is not avoided. (Chao, 2018)

In the implementation instrument Land value reference in Germany, Sweden, and Taiwan, Land value reference is one instrument important practical in policy land. One possible way emulated, namely Germany, which has a board of judges price land. The Appraisal board can become a tool in evaluating price land with routine and publishing price land by officials to society, which will create land market transparency and prevent the existence of speculators' land. When land market transparency already happens and not existence speculators' land so will lower the level of inequality in the ownership of land that occurs.

This way can be done in the Margamulya Village so that the public will not again be confused and will be weighed by the price of land sold and bought. This Thing will prevent the existence of speculators' land and prevent the existence price of too much land tall or too low. So that Public Margamulya Village no again weighs the price of land from zoning or only desires seller or buyer. With this method, the public can buy land at a price following, which will lower the level of inequality in the ownership of land.

II. Added Value Capturing

Margamulya Village community majority is a peasant. The land is a Thing important in life, specifically for farming. Because of that problem land, not easy Thing for avoided. Margamulya Village Community understands scoring the land he owns, which can be seen from the method community has action preventive like when there is speculators' land or land brokers Public direct report to the head village or the nearest RT RW. Then later, anticipation was conducted by briefing the public about low prices for no-sell land and influenced by speculators' land.

Although once exist existence usurpation land because not enough existence information is clear about ownership of land even though they have letters complete at the office village clan. Robbery land conducted with the method gathers mass and direct installs peg land; this also happened because of the provocateur's existence. The cause is the party who wants to build and need land of about 300Ha and new could around 150Ha. Besides that, people asked the public to sell the land at a specific price causing peasants to lose the land. The person the rent returned to purchased land at a low price.

Village community clan very knowing about score land, so that not easy for deceived. So far, this isn't it yet; once there are speculators incoming land to the village clan. Of course not; there are governing rules about score land, but the Public rate it alone. The land zone development only influences land value in the village clan. Land value changes when changing the zoning on the ground or upgrading access to land. For example, where previously there was no access to the land, the value of the land was low, and the price of the land would also be low. However, when there is access to the land, there is an immediate increase in land value and the price of the land.

Instrument Added Value Capturing is also an instrument that can be considered in policy land in Indonesia. Instrument this supports existence planning use land. With the existence score plus land, planning land use will be easier for conducting.

For example, some countries use instrument scores plus land, namely Switzerland and England. In Switzerland, the rating Added Value Capturing was conducted with two methods: determination related to entitlement zone change development and use, and the second is a determination by repeated. Determination score prime land, tax on score plus yielded land, is the tax used for compensation and land protection. Using tax brings the Government to prioritize land use with a score plus a high economy because it will give more income tall compared with use with a score more land low. (Viallon, 2018)

Unlike Switzerland, England uses this instrument to adapt land use with planning land. Development carried out must follow planning land. Added value land very take effect to plan vice versa. If any development is carried out outside planning so will occur enhancement of the score land suddenly, while if there is usage land not following planning that has been set previously, so will lower score land. (Askew, 2018)

The added value of land must be assessed regularly and then published to establish transparency of information about the land. The value will determine the planning that will be carried out in the land zone. This will also increase the distribution of land use so that there is no longer very expensive and very cheap land. Fair land use will also be a bright spot for regional inequality problems.

III. Land Taxation

The people of the Margamulya Village, the majority of whom are peasants, are landless peasants or arable peasants. The land used is owned by the corporation or the community, which owns the land and is rented out. The system is a rental with a price of five thousand rupiahs for each spear per year. It is crucial for the existence of tax instruments in land policy in Indonesia, given the high level of inequality in land ownership, especially in Bandung Regency. This inequality in land ownership also results in other inequalities, such as economic inequality, because the land is a commodity that only certain people have.

The people of Margamulya Village believe that taxes are an essential instrument in land policy to balance land ownership. However, what must be considered is that the policies made must still pay attention to the community. The main point in the tax instrument is that it must be clear, firm, and well-directed. If the tax instrument exists only as a formality, the goal of reducing inequality in land ownership will never end.

Progressive taxes increase with wealth, and large landowners usually have above-average financial resources. Taxes finance the better urban and rural services, the higher the property value, and the more significant the proportion of taxes in providing income to the state. The public administration must therefore be interested in a fair, orderly, efficient land taxation system that functions to generate stable income. However, it is necessary to monitor whether the tax method chosen can increase or decrease rents and what other effects on land depend on the type of land. Changing the land tax will cause social conflict if the tax used results in systematic gains or losses.

Land tax is a crucial policy instrument in land policy. This instrument is binding and also makes a good impact. Land taxes can bind unscrupulous individuals who invest in land by imposing a higher tax if the land ownership is above the regulation that should be according to the Law No.5 of 1960 on Basic Agrarian Principles (UUPA), namely, 2 hectares of land. This way, there will be no more competition in making the land an asset. This will reduce the level of inequality in land ownership.

Instrument land taxation has been carried out in several countries, such as Estonia, Germany, and the UK, with different taxes. Estonia applies tax score land in policy land. Tax this conducted with system evaluation score land without building, tax rate generally permanent without affected use land. Owner land cannot avoid tax if the character is fixed; one method to lower the burden tax is using land efficiently. Using instrument tax has an impact positively on the development of Estonian cities. (Thiel and Wenner, 2018)

Another country that uses tax as one instrument in policy his land is Germany. The system tax used is tax property. Results obtained from evaluation tax German are about effectiveness, tax property, and tax other could be used to Fulfill budget public or for produce affect incentives. In Germany and many other countries, holders of a key in even distribution of income and wealth For many years later, not power work, or capital, but land. (Löhr, 2018)

Apart from Estonia and Germany, the UK also uses instrument tax land. Taxes levied enough many, like capital gains tax, tax inheritance, and duty stamp duty. Capital gains tax is charged to various assets (including income stocks, savings, and profits from asset sales), although there is an exception for personal house individuals. Then there is tax inheritance; a tax levied on the Dead owner's land. Lastly, taxes duty stamp is a tax levied for the sale of a new property. Third, tax this enough to produce significant income but is quite sensitive to politics. (Layard, 2018)

Taxes used by other countries can become recommendations in Indonesia's policy land. Like tax score land that can be used to reach destination plan use land, with method those who use land by no efficient or even the one who made the land they abandoned will permanent worn same tax with owner land that uses land by efficient. This will reduce or even remove lands that are not used, hindering the productivity economy.

Taxes used by other countries, such as capital gains tax, tax inheritance, tax score land, and taxes duty stamp, are examples of a tax that can use by Indonesia to reduce inequality in land ownership. Taxes already used in Indonesian land are Land and Building Tax (PBB) as tax levied recurring, and Acquisition Duty of Right on Land and Building (BPHTB) as tax not repeated or same with tax duty stamp in England. However, they have a system with different collections and assessments but have the same goal. Taxes that apply in Indonesia in Thing tax property is as follows.

Figure 4. Property Tax in Indonesia

Source: Researcher, 2021.

Taxes levied on land are Land and Building Tax (PBB) and Acquisition Duty of Right on Land and Building (BPHTB). Land and Building Tax (PBB) is levied annually with base Imposition of Sales Value of Taxable Object (NJOP) or the average price obtained from transaction sell buy by reasonable. Acquisition Duty of Right on Land and Building (BPHTB) is the tax collected when transferring right or acquisition right now on land or building with base imposition, i.e., tax object acquisition value (NPOP) or price transaction land or building. Taxes this Indonesia has long used as one of the instruments in policy land. However tax - tax cannot reduce land ownership inequality in Indonesia. Taxes not yet can deter the people who make the land as an asset or real investment make many the land that; makes many lands not used.

Policy land taxation needed to reduce inequality ownership is tax progressive for land. Tax must be imposed on land that is not productive or idle (idle) and also productive land. Taxes to be worn are progressive final tax, tax on profit score land (capital gains tax), and non-tax utilized (unutilized assets). There is a reason why tax progress must quickly be applied: tax will increase the productivity economy and improve state income using idle land. With applied tax progress, many idle lands soon did business, built property, or were utilized by the community, which will also reduce unemployment. This Thing will open new fieldwork and improve the economy.

Tax progress on land ownership will prevent the owners of capital from owning land with a scope wide so that peasants can work and not again exploited. This could be conducted with the use adjustment rate on Land and Building Tax (PBB) or Acquisition Duty of Right on Land and Building (BPHTB) over acquisition land. At the same time, idle land could periodically apply adjustment tariffs on the United Nations.

Village community clans agree if there is discourse imposition tax progressive to the owner's land. This Thing, as one villager said, Margamulya Village said that tax progress that good for conducted for pushing the well-being of people and encourages, so that occur balance Among ownership of land and peasants. However, the imposition of tax must be noticed by those wearing it because they fear that if tax is too much worn to all who have land, more from limit maximum regulation will impact the price rent of the land they work on.

The policy must take into account the condition of the community. As happened in Margamulya Village, when the land owned by the village government, which was leased to peasants, was about to be taken over by the government, the people became angry with the reason that the land had been rented out since time immemorial. Meanwhile, if the village government raises the rental price of the land, the government is concerned about the condition of peasants whose harvests are not fixed. Likewise, if we implement the policy, we must pay attention to the objectives of the policy clearly so as not to increase the burden on peasants who are already difficult.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research and discussion instrument results, policy land is not optimal in reducing land ownership inequality. Instrument- existing in Indonesia policy land still does not yet have the practical instrument like Land Value Reference, Added Value Capturing, and Land Taxation. Land Value Reference is not yet in policy land in Indonesia; so far, this is used in Sales Value of Taxable Object (NJOP) or estimation precise individual different with Land Value Reference official from Government, so no land market transparency exists. Then Added Value Capturing is only determined by development zoning land, so case speculators' land still often happens. Besides that, the tax applied to land was not enough to deter the ruling community land, so the needed policy tax more land bind and giving effect deterrent to person-person ruler land.

Based on the research findings, this study suggests the following recommendations: First, based on the information, no existing Land Value Reference by an official from the Government needs to conduct an evaluation land routine a reference in giving Land Value Reference by the official to society. Second, With a lack of understanding Public about the Added Value Capturing brings up speculators' land. Socialization about the score land needs to be conducted so that the community does not easily Trick speculators' land and society understands the score of the land he owns. Third, land taxation used in Indonesia can still not give effect deterrent to person-person ruler land; other than that effect from mastery, this is too much creation of lands that are not productive. Because of that, they needed to tax more land bind and give effect deterrent to person - the person that. However, with notes, policy tax must have a clear and precise target. Lastly, With no existing instrument practical in policy land in Indonesia, then policy land in Indonesia needs to be formulated repeat for purpose even if distribution ownership land can materialize.

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